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Investigations on Thermally Induced Delamination in Mechanically Joined Carbon Fiber Composites

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Motivation and objective

- Multi-material design of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) and metals in small automotive series
- Efficient joining technology for hybrid joints necessary
- Combination of mechanical joining technologies and adhesive bonding
- Damages in self-piercing riveted CFRP during heat treatment in the paint shop

- Analyzing the effects of thermally induced damages
- Development of suitable counter measures to minimize damages

Process sequence of self-piercing riveting (SPR) with full rivet

Used materials

- Rivets (measures in mm)

FRP	CF-EP	CF-EP2	CF-PA 66
Fiber	Carbon	Carbon	Carbon
Textile / Layup	UD-Layers (0/90) _{5s}	UD-Layers (0/90) _{5s}	Twill 2/2 8 Layers
Polymer	Epoxy resin	Epoxy resin	Polyamide 6.6
Glass transition temperature	130 °C	194 °C	70 °C
Fiber content	51 vol.-%	51 vol.-%	51 vol.-%
Metals	HC340LA	EN AW-6181	
Tensile strength	410 - 510 MPa	215 MPa	
Yield strength	340 - 420 MPa	105 MPa	
Elongation at break	≥ 24 %	≥ 21 %	

Thermally induced damages in self-piercing riveted CFRP-metal joints

- Occurrence of delamination, fiber breaks and inter-fiber failure after heating
- Compression failure of 0° and 90° Unidirectional layers
- Radial compressive stress induced by stamping of rivet

Material
CF-EP; t = 2.0 mm HC340LA; t = 1.5 mm
Joining technology
Self-piercing riveting
Rivet
Type 094 733 000.900
Die
4.2 / 6.5 / 0.6 / 0.2x59°

Analyzing the stamping process

- Starting of conically converging cracks in the composite from the edge of the rivet foot
- Caused by shear stress induced by existing compressive and shear stress
- Undersized hole because of converging fracture path

[01]

Analyzing the stamping process

- Measuring punched holes after removing the rivet
- Diameter of punched holes significantly smaller than diameter of rivet shank
- Inducement of radial compressive stress (σ_R^-) during the joining process

Effect of glass transition temperature on thermally induced damages

- Occurrence of damages after exceeding the glass transition temperature
- Decreased stiffness of the matrix
- Reduced supporting effect

Material
CF-EP; t = 2.0 mm HC340LA; t = 1.5 mm
Joining technology
Self-piercing full riveting
Rivet
Type 094 733 000.900
Die
4.2 / 6.5 / 0.6 / 0.2x59°
Thermal treatment (30 min)
100 °C / 120 °C / 140 °C / 160 °C
DMA-parameters
NETZSCH DMA 242 3-point-bending 50 mm x 10 mm x 2 mm Testing frequency: 3.333 Hz

Countermeasures to minimize thermally induced damages

- Polymeric (PEEK) washers
- Steel clamping-washers
- Tolerance self-piercing rivet
- High performance thermoset matrix with glass transition temperature $> 180\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

Polymeric washer and clamping-washer

PEEK washer (a)

- Bending up of fibers during embossing due to lower stiffness of PEEK washer
- Reduction of radial compression stress

Clamping-washer (b)

- Clamping the CF-EP underneath the rivet head during stamping
- Increasing the diameter of punched hole
- Reduction of radial compression stress

High performance thermoset and tolerance rivet

High performance thermoset (c)

- Higher stiffness of the matrix at 180 °C
- Sustaining the supporting effect of the matrix
- No damages of the laminate despite radial compression stress

Tolerance rivet (d)

- Spring-back of the fibers into the tolerance area of the rivet shank
- No radial compressive stress induced in the composite portion during the joining process

Material	CF-EP2; t = 2.0 mm HC340LA; t = 1.5 mm
Joining technology	Self-piercing riveting
Rivet	Reservoir rivet
Countermeasure	Thermoset $T_g > 180$ °C
Material	CF-EP; t = 2.0 mm HC340LA; t = 1.5 mm
Joining technology	Self-piercing riveting
Rivet	Reservoir rivet
Countermeasure	Tolerance SPR

Influence of thermally induced damage on load bearing capacity under quasi static load

- Exemplary load-displacement curves
- No significant reduction of maximal shear-strength
- Lower first peak by the joint with heating treatment
- Lower stiffness of the joint after thermal treatment

Material
CF-EP; t = 2.0 mm
HC340LA; t = 1.5 mm
Measurements
CF-EP: 45 x 113 mm ²
HC340LA: 45 x 105 mm ²
Rivet
Reservoir rivet
Thermal treatment
Shown in diagram
Testing machine
Zwick 100
Testing speed
v = 10 mm/min
Shear test acc. to DVS/EFB 3480-1

Influence of thermally induced damage on load bearing capacity under cyclic load

- Elastic zone of the SN-curves shown
- Significant lower load bearing capacity under cyclic load after thermal treatment
- Mode of failure
 - Pull through failure
 - Rivet break

Testing method	Wöhler test
Testing frequency	f = 20 Hz
Stress ratio	R = 0.1
End criteria	Break
Rivet	Reservoir rivet
Thermal treatment	Shown in diagram
Material 1	CF-EP; t = 2.0 mm
Material 2	HC340LA; t = 1.5 mm
Measurements	CF-EP: 45 x 113 mm ² HC340LA: 45 x 105 mm ²
	Shear test acc. to DVS/EFB 3480-1

Summary

- Thermally induced damages in CFRP by self piercing riveted CFRP metal joints
 - Inducing radial compression stress in CFRP during the joining process
 - Exceeding the glass transition temperature due to heat treatment according to cathodic dip coating
- Influence of thermally induced damages on load bearing capacity
 - Reduction of joint stiffness
 - Reduction of shear load strength under cyclic load
- Development and validation of countermeasures
 - Clamping-washers → Homogenization of compressive stress
 - Tolerance rivet → Avoiding of radial compressive stress
 - High performance thermoset → Improved robustness during heat treatment

[01]: Augenthaler, F.: *Weiterentwicklung der Stanznietechnologie für das werkstoffgerechte Fügen von FKV-Metall-Verbindungen*. Dissertation. Shaker Verlag, 2018

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